

Advancing non-carbon energy: optimized and safely operated solid oxide fuel cell design for industrial feasibility

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ABSTRACT

As the world shift towards sustainable energy solutions, solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) using non-carbon fuels like ammonia and hydrogen emerge as promising pathways to produce clean energy and enhance conversion efficiency. However, current implementations encounter challenges such as nitriding effects from direct ammonia injection to the stack, overestimated benefits of anode off-gas (AOG) recirculation, and a sole focus on electrical efficiency that overlooks the thermal advantages of SOFCs. This study addresses these gaps through a comprehensive multi-objective optimization of SOFC systems fueled by ammonia and hydrogen, assessing their efficiency, fuel utilization, and heat exergy. The research translates material phenomena into mathematical constraints and quantifies the effects of control variables through systematic parameter variation. Results indicate that ammonia-fueled SOFC systems slightly outperform hydrogen, achieving an electrical efficiency of about 65% compared to 62% for hydrogen systems, although hydrogen demonstrates superior fuel utilization and exergy efficiency. Optimal AOG recirculation and NH₃ cracking fraction that do not compromise stack lifetime and stay in the safe operating zone of nitriding are identified. It also challenges the assumptions that a higher AOG recirculation can benefit performance, suggesting that more extensive AOG recirculation might not always enhance it. Soft sensors are provided to predict system's performance and enable proactive adjustments to facilitate industrial applications where some parameters, such as high-temperature stack's pressure drop, are costly or difficult to measure. This study significantly advances the practical deployment of SOFC technologies, enhancing their feasibility for sustainable energy development.

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1. Introduction

Recent studies have documented substantial shifts in global climate indicators, including rising sea levels, changes in global wind patterns, increased global temperatures, and diminishing polar ice caps. These changes are linked to the escalating concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, which are known to trap heat and contribute to global warming. While various sources contribute to these emissions, a significant proportion originates from

the burning of fossil fuels like coal, oil, and natural gas [1,2], which continue to dominate global energy supplies. Without significant measures to curb these emissions, it is expected that the atmospheric concentrations of these gases will continue to rise [3].

In addressing the challenges of climate change, there has been a marked shift towards renewable energy technologies that limit emissions. These technologies recorded nearly an 8% growth in 2022, highlighting their expanding role in the global energy landscape. Additionally, an increase in renewable energy production by 1% is associated with a reduction in emissions by 0.243%, demonstrating the vital role that renewable energy plays in mitigating the effects of climate change [4]. However, the integration of inherently intermittent renewable sources, such as solar and wind, due to their dependence on weather conditions, presents

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new challenges for energy supply. This variability necessitates robust energy storage and conversion solutions to ensure the reliability and stability of the electrical grid.

Solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) present a promising advancement in electricity generation technology. They are highly efficient in converting chemical energy directly into electricity, potentially enhancing users' grid independence and effectively discharging storage tanks [5]. The high conversion efficiency of SOFCs, combined with their ability to utilize a variety of fuels, renders them a versatile and sustainable option in the transition towards a less carbon-intensive energy infrastructure [6]. The reversible mode of SOFC (i.e., solid oxide electrolyzer) can be used to convert excess renewable energy into stored chemical energy. Integrating such technologies with fuel storage can mitigate the impact of renewable energy intermittency and contribute to a more energy-secure and sustainable future.

There are three primary strategies for using SOFCs to generate carbon-neutral electricity. In the first option, SOFC can utilize bio-fuels such as biomethane or bio-ethanol. Given that the fuel utilization rate of SOFC is approximately 0.85, some unconverted fuel remains downstream. Consequently, a burner is required to achieve complete combustion of the unconverted fuel. The CO₂ produced in this case is considered carbon-neutral. Nevertheless, integrating biofuel production with SOFC technology poses challenges, particularly in installing biofuel purification units. The second option involves the use of fossil fuels. In this case, a CO₂ capture unit must be installed downstream of the burner to maintain carbon neutrality. This addition could substantially increase the total cost and complexity when scaling up the system, depending on the carbon capture and storage (CCS) technology employed. The third option uses non-carbon fuels, such as hydrogen or ammonia (NH₃), which results in no CO₂ in the environment. This approach directly eliminates the issue of CO₂ co-production with electricity generation, offering a more straightforward path for achieving carbon neutrality, albeit with considerations for the production and handling of these alternative fuels.

Transitioning from traditional fossil fuels, which are major contributors to CO₂, to these renewable and non-carbon energy technologies is crucial to mitigate adverse climate effects [7]. This transition not only aids in reducing CO₂ released to the environment but also addresses the challenges of integrating intermittent renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind, into the energy grid. It is crucial to understand the current research advancements in SOFC technologies to appreciate what has been achieved so far. However, it is equally important to identify the bottlenecks currently facing the industry and to explore the gaps that this study could potentially fill. This dual focus will enhance the feasibility and effectiveness of SOFC technologies within the energy sector, paving the way for more sustainable energy solutions.

2. State of the art and motivation

2.1. Literature review

2.1.1. Hydrocarbon fuels in SOFC

There is extensive ongoing research into the utilization of carbon-based fuels in SOFCs. Laosiripojana et al. [8] examined the direct internal reforming of methane, methanol, and ethanol in SOFCs. This research study assessed catalytic steam reforming over Ni/YSZ anodes at high temperatures, revealing that methane and methanol could be effectively used without significant carbon deposition through careful adjustment of system operations. However, ethanol led to excessive carbon buildup, degrading the Ni/YSZ anode and necessitating pre-reforming. In addition to material degradation caused by carbon deposition, CO₂ production repre-

sents another significant aspect of SOFC research. Wei et al. [9] explored four CO₂ capture technologies, namely monoethanolamine absorption and membrane separation based post-combustion CO₂ capture, pressure swing adsorption and solid oxide electrolyzer cells (SOECs) based oxy-combustion followed by CO₂ separation, and also analyzed the integration of CO₂ capture technologies with SOFCs. Their findings indicated that the integrated system could achieve CO₂ purities close to 100% with an electrical efficiency of approximately 62%. The study highlighted the need for cost considerations, suggesting that system scale-up could enhance economic viability. Similarly, Diglio et al. [10] investigated the integration of sorption-enhanced steam methane reforming with SOFCs using a novel CaO/CuO/NiO catalyst. Assessing three operational stages, their results showed a high methane conversion efficiency (about 95%) and hydrogen yield, producing a concentrated CO₂ stream ready for storage. They recommended further research to improve material stability and to scale up the technology for industrial applications.

While the use of hydrocarbon fuels in SOFCs is well established, incorporating CO₂ capture is essential to enhance their environmental friendliness, which could delay implementation due to the complexities involved. Meanwhile, renewable fuels (bio-fuels and e-fuels) that are carbon-neutral offer an advantage as CO₂ can be released into the atmosphere. It is crucial to highlight that e-fuels must use biogenic CO₂ to close the carbon loop. Shiratori et al. [11] examined the direct feeding of biogas into a SOFC at high operating temperatures using Ni-ScSZ cermet as an anode material. The system maintained stable voltage without carbon deposition at 1000 °C over 50 h, and demonstrated resilience to H₂S contamination. The study highlighted a need for research into robust system designs that can adapt to variable biogas qualities and higher impurity concentrations without performance degradation. Further, Shiratori et al. [12] showed stable operation and effective carbon deposition mitigation by adjusting the air-to-biogas ratio.

2.1.2. H₂ fuel in SOFC

Non-carbon fuels offer a sustainable alternative, completely eliminating combustion pollutants during the SOFC process operation. Hydrogen is known for its high gravimetric energy density and environmentally friendly combustion process, which yields only water as the product [13]. The median value of GHG emissions from hydrogen production is around 2.9 kg-CO₂/kg-H₂, noting a reduction in emissions when operations shift from fossil to renewable electricity sources [14]. Wei et al. [1] analyzed environmental emissions from hydrogen production using various electrolyzer technologies and renewable energy types, achieving a minimum value of 0.96 kg-CO₂/kg-H₂. Consequently, employing hydrogen as a fuel in SOFCs emerges as a potentially sustainable solution.

Xue et al. [15] present an in-depth analysis of an innovative energy storage system that integrates compressed air energy storage with water electrolysis and a hydrogen-fueled SOFC combined with gas and steam turbine systems. This comprehensive system achieves a round-trip efficiency of 68.24% and an exergy efficiency of 64.28%. These efficiencies translate into significant energy savings and a relatively short payback period of 3.69 years. This analysis highlights the system's economic viability and contribution to zero-emission energy solutions.

Further, Marocco et al. [16] demonstrated that hydrogen and water vapor-fed SOFC systems can achieve enhanced thermal efficiency by operating at lower airflow rates, which reduces cooling requirements. Additionally, García-Camprubía et al. [17], utilizing computational fluid dynamics modelling, emphasized the importance of managing inlet gas temperature and velocity in hydrogen-fed SOFC to boost both efficiency and durability. These studies reveal that hydrogen can significantly bolster the

performance and economic viability of SOFC systems through improved heat management and operational efficiencies.

2.1.3. NH_3 fuel in SOFC

A significant challenge associated with hydrogen is its low volumetric energy density under normal conditions, necessitating storage at very high pressures. This requirement for high-pressure storage consequently leads to increased energy consumption during the compression process, impacting the overall efficiency of hydrogen as a fuel. Conversely, ammonia is gaining recognition as a promising alternative fuel for SOFC systems due to its high hydrogen content and capability to decompose into hydrogen and nitrogen without carbon emissions [18]. Compared with hydrogen, it offers more accessible storage and transport due to its higher volumetric energy density and the ability to be liquefied under mild conditions, coupled with an already established global infrastructure, making it particularly useful in SOFC applications. Conventional ammonia production via steam methane reforming and ammonia synthesis typically generates approximately 2.6 metric tons CO_2 -eq/metric ton ammonia. Alternative production methods, which utilize renewable energy sources for hydrogen production and cryogenic distillation for nitrogen extraction, can achieve a reduction in GHG emissions by up to 91% compared to the SMR pathway [19]. Additionally, SOFC operates at high temperatures, enabling the simultaneous generation of electricity and heat as co-products. The electrochemical reactions within the stack are exothermic, typically utilizing cathode air to supply necessary oxygen and to regulate stack temperature. If ammonia is introduced into the stack, a chemical reaction occurs, specifically, internal ammonia cracking, which is an endothermic process. Consequently, incorporating ammonia at the stack's inlet can facilitate a reduction in the cathode air flow rate, thereby diminishing the power consumption of the air blower.

Fuerte et al. [20] affirm the viability of ammonia as a fuel for SOFCs, highlighting its competitive cost, easy liquefaction, and safer handling. Additionally, Rathore et al. [21] provide a review of the advancements and prospects in direct ammonia SOFCs, focusing on the importance of anode design to enhance ammonia decomposition and noting its efficiency as a hydrogen carrier. However, using ammonia as fuel presents challenges, such as anode poisoning from by-products linked to activation, ohmic, and concentration over-potentials [22]. Wan et al. [23] also highlight the issue of anode degradation, suggesting the use of pre-decomposed ammonia to enhance cell longevity.

Building on the concept of efficient ammonia utilization, Omer et al. [24] investigated the design and performance of direct ammonia-fed planar SOFCs, finding that different flow configurations, co-flow, counter-flow, and cross-flow significantly affect performance due to varying temperature distributions and thermal stresses. The cross-flow configuration demonstrated the highest electrical efficiency, reaching 51.4% under specific conditions while also minimizing thermal stress, which is crucial for SOFC durability. Additionally, Selvam et al. [25] enhanced the SOFC system's operational viability by allowing 100% fuel utilization in a dead-end anode, significantly boosting energy and exergy efficiencies by eliminating the afterburner. Concurrently, Quach et al. [26] targeted small-scale SOFCs, increasing hydrogen content by extracting water from the recirculated anode off-gas, achieving electrical efficiency up to 67.5%. These studies highlight the importance of optimizing system configurations to maximize the efficiency and sustainability of ammonia-based SOFC systems.

On the durability and performance fronts, Wang et al. [27] focused on the stability of ammonia-powered SOFCs, noting stable cell performance across multiple thermal cycles without microstructural damage. This underscores the robustness of

ammonia-fed fuel cells under fluctuating thermal conditions. Concurrently, Meng et al. [28] delved into comparative performance analyses. The study revealed that ammonia yields lower power density compared to hydrogen due to the endothermic nature of its decomposition, suggesting the need for operational adjustments such as pre-heating.

Addressing the integration of ammonia in multi-generation systems, Qu et al. [29] and Ezzat et al. [30] discussed hybrid configurations that pair SOFC systems with other energy conversion technologies. Qu et al. evaluated a hybrid system that integrates an SOFC with an internal combustion engine fueled by ammonia, achieving electrical efficiencies above 65%. Similarly, Ezzat et al. reviewed advancements in integrated SOFC and gas turbine systems, achieving energy and exergy efficiencies of 58.78% and 50.66%, respectively. These configurations demonstrate the potential for multi-generation systems to efficiently utilize ammonia, contributing to a more sustainable energy landscape.

Additionally, Perna et al. [31] and Yilmaz et al. [32] explored the implications of integrating ammonia-fueled SOFCs into complex energy systems. Perna et al. assessed a combined heat, hydrogen, and power system that aims to produce a substantial quantity of hydrogen while supplying electricity and heat, achieving an overall tri-generation efficiency of 81%. Yilmaz et al. presented a design for a SOFC-based plant intended for efficient hydrogen production, achieving an energetic and exergetic efficiency of 61.04% and 57.13%, respectively, highlighting the effectiveness of integrating various energy conversion processes for enhancing system performance.

These studies highlight the transformative potential of hydrogen and ammonia as fuels in SOFC to produce electricity, aligning with global sustainability goals while addressing specific technical challenges to enhance system performance and reliability. The ongoing research collectively indicates a promising future for generating clean power from non-carbon fuels in energy systems.

2.2. Gaps and contribution

While numerous studies have explored the performance of SOFCs using ammonia as fuel, the effects of nitrating, particularly converting from material impact to system performance perspective, remain largely unexplored. The common practice of direct NH_3 injection into the stack, while prevalent in research, poses risks of long-term damage, making it unsuitable for industrial applications. Additionally, the impact of different anode-off-gas (AOG) recirculation methods on electrical efficiency has been underexplored, with limited consideration of the associated pressure drops within the stack. Excessive recirculation flow can lead to high-pressure drops, potentially compromising stack design—an issue largely overlooked in system modelling and optimization. Furthermore, despite the multi-functional nature of SOFC systems, which can generate both electricity and heat for industrial applications, most studies have focused on electrical efficiency, neglecting their broader potential.

This research study addresses key challenges in SOFC technology by introducing advancements that enhance system design and operational realism. A significant contribution is the integration of SOFC cell material degradation phenomena into system performance analysis, which prevents excessive ammonia injection and mitigates potential stack damage. Additionally, while previous studies have employed external ammonia crackers to control the cracking fraction, they often treat this as a sensitivity analysis and fail to incorporate kinetic behaviour. This omission prevents reactor performance from adapting to operational temperature changes, thereby limiting the range of optimal conditions. In this study, a kinetic reactor model is integrated into the optimization

framework, enabling more accurate and dynamic performance evaluations.

Additionally, this study explores the incorporation of no, cold and warm AOG recirculation in both hydrogen- and ammonia-fueled SOFC systems to enhance overall fuel utilization. Warm recirculation is conventionally employed and extensively studied in existing literature [33]; it can lead to increase in AOG blower power consumption, thereby reducing system efficiency. This research goes beyond the typical sensitivity analysis of recirculation fractions commonly found in current studies. Instead, it optimizes the recirculation flow rate by carefully considering the pressure drops across the stack, ensuring that operational parameters do not exceed safe limits or compromise the stack's integrity. This method proves especially viable for real-world industrial applications, offering a practical approach to improving efficiency while maintaining system safety and performance.

This study employs multi-objective optimization to simultaneously evaluate electrical efficiency, global fuel utilization, and heat performance in hydrogen- and ammonia-fueled SOFC systems. This approach enables a detailed comparison of the two fuels, highlighting their respective advantages and limitations to support informed decision-making by industrial partners. Furthermore, a comprehensive parametric analysis utilizing the Monte Carlo method explores the relationships between operating parameters and key performance indicators. Unlike conventional sensitivity analyses that mainly describe performance trends, this research derives precise mathematical equations that serve as advanced predictive soft sensors. These models enable accurate performance forecasting and ensure safe operations, significantly improving SOFC system design and operation in both industrial and research contexts. Lastly, the integration of a Rankine cycle (RC) into both systems examines the potential for waste heat valorization. This initiative aims to enhance overall electrical efficiency and emphasizes the use of exergy as a key metric for evaluating heat recovery potential.

In summary, this study makes significant contributions to the advancement of SOFC technology by addressing key research gaps and introducing innovative solutions that improve system performance, operational safety, reliability, and sustainability. By enhancing SOFC system design, this research establishes new benchmarks for future studies and industrial applications while promoting the development of more sustainable energy solutions.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. SOFC system fueled by NH₃ or H₂

Fig. 1 depicts the process flow diagram of the SOFC system fueled by ammonia or hydrogen. For the ammonia-fueled process, ammonia is heated (H1 and H2) to a specified temperature before being introduced into the ammonia cracker. The outlet of the cracker mainly consists of N₂ and H₂, with residual NH₃. This gas mixture is subsequently reheated (H3) to achieve the optimal operating temperature required by the SOFC stack. Once at the desired temperature, the gas mixture is injected into the anodic side of the SOFC stack, where chemical energy is converted into electricity.

In contrast, when hydrogen is used as the fuel, both ammonia cracker and heater H3 are bypassed. Instead, heaters H1 and H2 directly heat the hydrogen to the requisite inlet temperature for the SOFC stack. In contrast to hydrocarbon fuel-based SOFC systems, such as those utilizing methane, which require steam to prevent carbon deposition and perform reforming, hydrogen or ammonia-based systems do not require steam. This distinction highlights a key advantage of non-carbon fuels, as they simplify

the SOFC system and reduce the operational complexities associated with steam management.

Air is preheated (H4) before entering into the cathodic side of the SOFC stack. The introduction of air serves two primary functions: firstly, it supplies the necessary oxygen for the electrochemical reactions within the stack; secondly, it maintains the stack temperature by manipulating the air flow rate. The maximum single pass fuel utilization rate is about 0.85 for the SOFC stack, so the anodic side outlet stream contains unconverted NH₃ or H₂. This anode-off gas (AOG) is then divided into two streams. One stream is cooled (C2) to partially condense the water. Subsequently, it is compressed by an AOG blower to balance the pressure drops in the system, allowing it to mix with the freshly heated fuel. The second stream is directed to a burner where fresh air is introduced to supply oxygen for the complete combustion of the unconverted fuel and maintain the maximum operating temperature of the burner. The exhaust gases from the burner are then cooled (C3) to separate water from the remaining gases. Cathode outlet air can also be used and injected into the burner, but it is not considered in this study.

3.2. SOFC system modelling

The process flowsheets for this study were developed in Aspen Plus v14.0. This section outlines the main input parameters and relevant modelling assumptions utilized in developing these flowsheets, ensuring clarity and reproducibility of the results presented in the subsequent sections.

3.2.1. Ammonia cracker

For the NH₃-fueled SOFC system, integrating an ammonia cracker is essential instead of directly injecting NH₃ into the stack, which could lead to nitriding and subsequent stack damage. The ammonia cracking reaction is outlined in Reaction (1).

The conversion fraction in the ammonia cracker depends on operating temperature, pressure, and the type of catalyst used. In this study, the operating pressure of the ammonia cracker is set at 1 bar to simplify its integration with the SOFC stack that operates near atmospheric pressure. The catalyst selected for this study is Ru/γ-Al₂O₃, a common choice well-documented in the existing literature. Conversion ratios relative to reactor temperature are drawn from Karim et al. [34], which has been validated experimentally. The cracking temperature in this study ranged from 300 to 500 °C, achieving conversion rates from 0 to 95%. Mathematical equations representing the cracking experiment outcome were extracted and included in the analysis. However, as the focus of this study is not on the detailed cracking dynamics, no further experimental validations were conducted. The equations derived from the experimental data are good enough for the purposes of this research.

3.2.2. SOFC stack and system model

The SOFC stack model was developed based on the published research studies. Specifically those outlined and validated in Wang et al. [35] and the European project [36]. Since the main focus of this study is not on model validation, these details are not elaborated extensively. The parameters for the stack and system models are detailed in our previously published work, ensuring their reliability and accuracy for the current study [33]. Like methane, which can undergo internal reforming inside the SOFC stack, ammonia can also engage in a cracking reaction within the stack, as described in Reaction (1). This reaction converts ammonia into H₂ and N₂, an endothermic chemical reaction. The electrochemical

Fig. 1. Process flow diagram of a SOFC system fueled by ammonia or hydrogen.

reactions occur at the anode and cathode sides, detailed in Reactions (2) and (3), respectively. The primary inputs for the SOFC stack and system model are presented in Table 1.

As stated above, NH_3 can directly crack inside the SOFC stack, a process the industry favours due to its endothermic nature. It helps in balancing the heat released by the electrochemical reactions and reduces the need for fresh air to control the stack temperature. Consequently, less power is required by the air blower, enhancing the electrical efficiency of the SOFC system. However, excessive ammonia within the stack may lead to a nitriding effect, potentially damaging the stack. Therefore, injecting an appropriate quantity of ammonia into the stack without causing a nitriding effect is crucial.

The nitriding potential (K_n) is quantified based on the input anode flow to the stack, precisely the mole fraction of ammonia and hydrogen. To prevent nitriding and ensure safe stack operation, K_n must stay below its critical limit ($K_{n,\text{crit}}$), which is closely related to the inlet operating temperature of the stack. In this study, K_n is determined using Aspen Plus simulations, and then it is compared to $K_{n,\text{crit}}$, with reference data sourced from Rizvandi et al. [37]. This approach ensures that the SOFC operates within safe limits, optimizing the performance while avoiding damage from nitriding.

Besides preventing the nitriding effect, ensuring the safe operation of the SOFC stack involves carefully managing the maximum temperature (less than 100 °C) and pressure differences (less than 100 mbar) across the stack (along the flow direction). The temperature difference across the stack can be controlled by adjusting the fresh air flow rate on the cathode side. However, managing the pressure drops across the stack is more complex due to multiple

influencing factors. This complexity is captured in Eq. (1), which includes several parameters to account for variations in system dynamics across the gas diffusion layer (GDL) of the stack's cathode and anode. These parameters integrate aspects like fluid dynamics and material characteristics, highlighting the intricacies of maintaining optimal operating conditions within the stack.

$$dP(\dot{m}, \rho, \mu) = C_{\text{GDL}} \cdot \dot{m} \cdot \frac{\rho_{\text{ref}}}{\rho} \cdot \frac{\mu}{\mu_{\text{ref}}} \quad (1)$$

The C_{GDL} is a coefficient associated with the GDL for fuel or air and represents the resistive properties inherent to the material and structure of the GDL. The term \dot{m} represents the mass flow rate of the fluid (fuel or air) moving through a specific section per unit of time. The ratio ρ_{ref}/ρ adjusts the calculation based on deviations from a reference density ρ_{ref} , accommodating changes in the compressibility or temperature of the fluid. For the cathode side, ρ_{ref} is 0.4 kg/m³ and for the anode side, it is 0.2 kg/m³. Similarly, μ/μ_{ref} compensates for variations in the viscosity of the fluid (reference value: $\mu_{\text{ref}} = 5\text{E-}05$ Pa·s for the cathode side and $\mu_{\text{ref}} = 3\text{E-}05$ Pa·s for the anode side), which may be affected by temperature or other environmental factors. Together, these components calculate the dynamic pressure drops across the GDL of the stack, reflecting the impacts of flow rate, density and viscosity changes on pressure drops. All reference values have been provided by the stack manufacturing company.

3.3. Multi-objective optimization

The multi-objective optimization (MOO) problems have been solved using OSMOSE, an optimization framework developed by the Industrial Process and Energy Systems Engineering (IPESE) laboratory at the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), as presented in Fig. 2. OSMOSE is capable of interfacing with external MOO tools such as Dakota [38,39] and flow sheeting software such

Table 1
Design and operating specifications of SOFC system; OT: operating temperature.

Specification	Value	Specification	Value
Stack capacity, kW	10	AOG blower maximum OT, °C	280
Stack area, m ²	~3	AOG blower discharge pressure, bar	1.25
Current density, A/cm ²	0.4	AOG blower mechanical efficiency, –	0.85
Air blower mechanical efficiency, –	0.85	AOG blower isentropic efficiency, –	0.8
Air blower isentropic efficiency, –	0.8	Burner operating temperature, °C	900

Fig. 2. Process integration and optimization via OSMOSE.

as Aspen Plus. This integration facilitates the optimization of processes modelled in Aspen Plus by enabling the transfer of decision variable values to the process model and the retrieval of crucial data from the process model. OSMOSE conducts mass and energy integration by formulating a mixed integer linear programming (MILP) problem. This MILP problem utilizes process and utility models to determine optimal interconnections and optimize mass and heat flows. Whenever MOO method generates a new set of decision variables, this information is transferred to the system model in Aspen Plus, where it is processed as inputs. After convergence of system simulation, the system outcomes are extracted by OSMOSE, and subsequently utilized in MILP problem formulation and also in computing objective functions for MOO. The MILP problem is solved using the AMPL/CPLEX solver (version 20210220, MS VC++ 10.0, 64-bit), ensuring robust and efficient optimization. Finally, OSMOSE provides optimal results for objective functions, decision variables, and the selection or sizing of utilities, alongside generating various types of heat curves.

This study has considered three objective functions: electrical efficiency, heat exergy and global fuel utilization, detailed in Table 2. Eq. (2) defines the electrical efficiency η for the SOFC system, which is computed as the ratio of the net power output to the energy input as fuel. P_{SOFC} represents the power output from the stack, and P_{aux} denotes the power consumed by auxiliary components within the system. The term \dot{m}_{fuel} indicates the mass flow rate of the fuel, and LHV_{fuel} refers to the lower heating value of the fuel.

$$\eta = \frac{P_{\text{SOFC}} - P_{\text{aux}}}{\dot{m}_{\text{fuel}} \times LHV_{\text{fuel}}} \quad (2)$$

Eq. (3) quantifies the exergy, or usable energy, that can be derived from a heat transfer process [40]. Here, B represents the exergy, Q denotes the amount of heat transferred, T is the temperature at which the heat is transferred, and T_0 is the ambient or reference temperature [41]. The term T_0/T reflects the ambient temperature relative to the temperature of the heat source within the system. The expression $(1 - T_0/T)$, which is known as the Carnot factor, signifies the maximal efficiency with which the heat can be converted into work, assuming the process is reversible. This value decreases as the heat source temperature approaches the ambient temperature, indicating lower exergy and, thus, lower potential to perform work. Therefore, in this study, exergy is established as one of the objective functions which is essential for evaluating the quality of heat available from the SOFC system. Finally, global fuel utilization has been selected as the third objective function due to its ability to enhance the AOG recirculation fraction. This enhancement allows the stack to operate with lower single-pass fuel utilization, thereby extending the lifetime of the stack.

Table 2

SOFC optimization model specifications.

Objective functions	
Electrical efficiency	Maximize
Exergy	Maximize
Global fuel utilization	Maximize
Decision variables	
NH ₃ cracker temperature (CrackT), °C	300–500
NH ₃ input (FI), mol/s	0.051–0.067
H ₂ input (FI), mol/s	0.070–0.085
AOG recirculation fraction, –	0–0.9
AOG recirculation condensation temperature (CondT), °C	35–280
Temperature difference across stack (ΔT), °C	30–100
Constraints	
Stack single-pass fuel utilization, –	>0.2 and <0.90
SOFC anode side pressure drops, mbar	<100
SOFC cathode side pressure drops, mbar	<100
Mole fraction of the unconverted fuel at stack outlet, –	>0.1
Nitriding effect for NH ₃ fueled SOFC, –	$K_n < K_{n,\text{crt}}$

The evolutionary MOO method has been selected over the weighted sum method for generating the Pareto front, as it effectively identifies a set of optimal solutions representing the necessary trade-offs among conflicting objectives without giving undue priority to any single one. Each point on the Pareto front represents a viable trade-off, where any improvement in one objective would result in the deterioration of at least one other. This approach is particularly advantageous in complex decision-making environments where stakeholders have varying priorities, enabling them to select the most suitable solutions from the spectrum provided by the Pareto front to meet their specific requirements [42].

$$B = Q \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T} \right) \quad (3)$$

This study has several important decision variables, including ammonia cracker temperature, NH₃ or H₂ mole flow rate, AOG recirculation fraction, and AOG recirculation condensation temperature. Additionally, to avoid potential material damage, the temperature difference across the stack must always be kept below 100 °C and is controlled by adjusting the cathode air flow rate. Consequently, this study incorporates the maximum temperature differential across the stack as one decision variable. It establishes the stack operating temperature at the anode outlet as a constant 750 °C (maximum 850 °C) for both ammonia and hydrogen systems provided by the stack manufacturer. AOG recirculation fraction is set from 0 to 0.9, with the recirculation temperature

ranging from 30 to 280 °C (based on market available AOG blower specification). These ranges accommodate no AOG, cold AOG and warm AOG recirculation using a conventional blower designed to withstand temperatures up to 280 °C. The decision to avoid hot AOG recirculation stems from the significant cost and specific material requirements needed for blowers capable of handling higher temperatures, which also tend to have lower efficiency, approximately 0.6 [33]. Although an ejector could serve as an alternative method for hot recirculation, it would require customized designs for each configuration, posing challenges for scaling up.

Moreover, several constraints have been incorporated into the optimization framework to ensure that the model's optimal outcomes apply to industrial settings. For instance, maximum single-pass fuel utilization (FU) is set at 0.9, ensuring that more than 10% of the unconverted fuel remains downstream of the stack. However, operating the stack at a very low FU is impractical; therefore, a minimum FU threshold is established at 0.2. Additionally, the pressure drops on the anode and cathode sides of the stack are calculated in Aspen Plus. Respecting the manufacturing constraints by limiting the maximum pressure drops below 100 mbar is crucial. Lastly, the conversion rate in the ammonia cracker depends on its operating temperature; care must be taken to prevent excessive unconverted ammonia from reaching the stack, which could lead to nitriding effects. Thus, the nitriding potential must always remain below the critical nitriding value ($K_{n,crt}$) to avoid any damage to the stack.

3.4. Estimation of relative contributions

Estimation of correlations among decision variables and objective functions is essential for assessing their impacts and for the development of models that can be utilized in diverse settings. To address this, the current research aims to create simplified mathematical correlations or surrogate models. The developed models will enable both industrial practitioners and laboratory researchers, who may lack comprehensive measurement equipment, to estimate critical parameters such as electrical efficiency, global fuel utilization, heat exergy, pressure drops on the cathode and anode sides and nitriding impact. Such correlations are crucial for ensuring safe operations and gaining an understanding of system performance.

Linear regression is used to estimate the relationship between a dependent variable and several independent variables. In this study, linear regression is employed to quantify the relative contributions of each decision variable to the objective functions and some essential constraints, thereby providing empirical formulas with outstanding fitting performance. Considering the decision variable space (x) composed of independent variables, each outcome (y) can be defined by a linear equation, as shown by Eq. (4).

$$y = C_0 + C_1 \cdot x_1 + C_2 \cdot x_2 + \dots + C_n \cdot x_n; C_i: \text{regression coefficients} \quad (4)$$

The regression coefficients (C_i) are estimated using uniformly distributed data sets generated through approximately 1500 Monte Carlo simulations. Moreover, each variable and outcome are normalized, avoiding different orders of magnitude, often leading to statistical inaccuracies. A constant term (C_0), known as the intercept, is also required for performing linear regression. In this study, normalized linear coefficients will be referred to as C_i^* and real coefficients as C_i . Each coefficient is verified using statistical metrics such as p-values and confidence intervals to assess the reliability of the linear regression model. The null hypothesis (H_0) states that the estimated outcome is completely independent of the variables and that there is no apparent relationship between them. Further, a p-value below a given threshold ($\alpha = 0.05$) is necessary to reject the null hypothesis and assert that the estimated

coefficients are statistically significant. This work presents only statistically significant coefficients, along with their 95%-CI (confidence interval).

In some cases, the relationship between variables can be complex and non-linear, resulting in poor performance from linear regression models. To address this, polynomial regression or machine learning techniques can be helpful [43]. As the primary objective of this study is to provide tangible and simplistic equations for key performance indicators, machine learning algorithms are used only in very specific cases. For instance, to visualize the importance and directional impact of some variables, where the relation is highly non-linear, Shapley additive explanations (SHAP) are utilized. This powerful technique, derived from game theory, connects optimal credit allocation with local explanations of a machine-learning algorithm [44].

3.5. Waste heat valorization

SOFC operates at high temperatures, enabling it to produce electricity and co-generate high-quality heat. This generated heat can be utilized in two different ways. Firstly, it can produce steam at various pressure levels to meet specific requirements, such as industrial processes requiring high-temperature heat. This application effectively maximizes the system's available exergy after internal heat integration. Secondly, high-temperature waste heat can be converted into electricity using various technologies, such as by integrating a micro gas turbine based on organic Rankine cycle [45] or combining a turbo-compressor based on inverted Brayton cycle [46], potentially improving electrical efficiency by 5%–10% [47]. This demonstrates the combined heat and power capabilities of SOFC systems. While this study does not primarily focus on determining the most optimal waste heat valorization technologies, it does integrate a steam Rankine cycle (RC). This choice is driven by the RC's widespread market availability in commercial sizes and its economic feasibility, especially when integrated with large-scale SOFC systems, effectively showcasing the potential for heat utilization, thereby enhancing the overall round-trip efficiency of the system. Although the modelling and design specifics of the RC are not detailed here, but can be found in previously published studies [9].

4. SOFC system performance analysis

In this section, the performance of the SOFC system, fueled by either NH_3 or H_2 , is evaluated with a focus on the trade-offs among three conflicting objective functions through multi-objective optimization. Linear regression models are then developed to establish the relationships between decision variables and objective functions, enabling a clearer understanding of how operating parameters influence system performance. These correlations utilize only readily measurable variables, providing practical tools for industry to analyze and improve performance.

Furthermore, this study addresses real-world design considerations for both SOFC systems, including the evaluation of pressure drops and nitriding effects in the NH_3 -fueled system, as well as the impact of anode-off-gas recirculation fraction and single-pass fuel utilization on electrical efficiency. These findings lay a foundation for advancing SOFC technology, supporting its broader implementation in sustainable energy systems and enabling future innovations in design and operation.

4.1. Performance comparison between NH_3 - and H_2 -fueled SOFC systems

Before conducting the detailed performance analysis, it is essential to first assess the overall performance of the two systems.

Fig. 3. Pareto-optimal solutions (electrical efficiency, GFU and heat exergy) for (a) NH_3 -fueled and (b) H_2 -fueled SOFC systems.

Fig. 3(a) showcases the NH_3 -fueled SOFC system Pareto solutions for electrical efficiency, global fuel utilization (GFU) and heat exergy. The range of electrical efficiency varies from 48.3% to 64.7%, GFU from 0.69 to 0.91 and heat exergy from 1.70 to 3 kW. The results indicate that the maximum electrical efficiency (64.7%) is paired with a GFU of 0.91 and a heat exergy of 1.70 kW. Conversely, the highest recorded heat exergy (2.94 kW) occurs at a lower electrical efficiency (48.3%). This inverse relationship highlights that higher electrical efficiency generally results in lower available exergy, reflecting the principle that chemical energy can either be transformed into electricity or heat in SOFC system. A similar trend is observed between GFU and heat exergy, where GFU indicates the extent of fuel consumption after recirculation. Unlike the other relationships, the correlation between GFU and electrical efficiency does not follow a singular trend but instead shows varied clustered trends. This variability suggests that at similar electrical efficiency levels, GFU can differ significantly.

For the H_2 -fueled SOFC system, similar to the NH_3 -fueled system, three objective functions and four decision variables have been selected, with the external cracker being bypassed. Fig. 3(b) shows the obtained Pareto front, efficiency ranges from 51% to 62%, global fuel utilization varies from 0.82 to 0.98, and heat exergy varies from 3.03 to 4.03 kW. Unlike the NH_3 -fueled SOFC system, which exhibited consistent trends between electrical efficiency and heat exergy, as well as GFU and heat exergy, the H_2 -fueled system presents more clustered trends. The Pareto front indicates that the system can exhibit a range of GFU and heat exergy values at a given electrical efficiency level. Such variability suggests a complex interplay among decision variables, where some may exert conflicting influences on the objective functions, contributing to diverse performance.

It is valuable to gain a deeper understanding of the Pareto solutions for the NH_3 - and H_2 -fueled SOFC systems. As illustrated in Table 3, one solution with maximum efficiency (A- NH_3 and A- H_2) has been selected for each system, along with one solution with around 50% efficiency (B- NH_3 and B- H_2) for each system. For the NH_3 -fueled system, maximum efficiency approaches 65%, which is attributable to the ability of the NH_3 fuel, similar to CH_4 , to generate more power in the stack. In contrast, the H_2 -fueled system achieves a maximum efficiency of nearly 62%.

As expected, the solutions with maximum efficiencies (A- NH_3 and A- H_2) have lower fuel input compared to the solutions with about 50% efficiencies. The GFU for the H_2 -fueled system can reach up to 0.986, surpassing the maximum GFU (0.908) for the

NH_3 -fueled system. This limitation for the NH_3 -fueled system is primarily due to the risk of nitriding, necessitating a certain percentage of hydrogen downstream of the stack. Table 3 also presents pressure drops across the stack for the anode and cathode sides, and the reported values are well below the upper limit (i.e., 100 mbar). Further, a big proportion of ammonia (cracking fraction: 0.928 and 0.883) is cracked in the external cracker to avoid the nitriding impact, as a higher cracker temperature leads to more cracking of ammonia.

The non-dominated solutions with maximum efficiencies have similar total energy input: 16.23 kW for A- NH_3 , and 16.93 kW for A- H_2 . Despite its higher electrical efficiency, the NH_3 -fueled system generates less high-quality heat, resulting in a lower heat exergy of 1.7 kW. In contrast, the H_2 -fueled system achieves significantly higher heat exergy, approximately 3.03 kW. When comparing the A- NH_3 and B- H_2 solutions, the AOG blower power consumption is comparable for similar recirculation flow rates in both systems, though for different reasons. In the NH_3 -fueled system, despite a lower AOG condensation temperature, which ensures that all steam is condensed into water, the presence of N_2 in the AOG flow still contributes to increased blower power consumption. Conversely, in the H_2 system, the blower power consumption is primarily influenced by the presence of steam, as the AOG condensation temperature is higher, near 72 °C.

The overall efficiency for four chosen solutions, incorporating both electrical and thermal efficiencies, has been calculated. The H_2 -fueled system demonstrates superior performance, particularly for lower-efficiency solutions, achieving an overall efficiency of 71.06%. This suggests that operating the stack in a sub-optimal manner for electrical output can be beneficial if the cogeneration of heat is also a priority. Finally, a Rankine cycle has been integrated to convert waste heat into electricity, illustrating the impact of technology for utilizing the excess heat. Both H_2 - and NH_3 -fueled systems exhibit comparably high performance, achieving around 85% electrical efficiency with the additional electricity generated by the RC. The choice of operation mode may vary depending on customer requirements, but these findings highlight the flexibility of both systems in simultaneously delivering power and heat.

However, to gain a thorough understanding of the complex interplay between objective functions and decision variables, relying solely on Pareto solutions may not provide a comprehensive view. Therefore, this study has expanded its approach by applying Monte Carlo simulations on both systems to gather a large number of feasible solutions, thereby exploring the entire decision variable

Table 3Details of objective functions, decision variables, constraints, materials, and energy flow for selected solutions from NH₃- and H₂-fueled SOFC systems.

	NH ₃ -fueled SOFC system		H ₂ -fueled SOFC system	
	A-NH ₃	B-NH ₃	A-H ₂	B-H ₂
FI, mol/s	0.051	0.064	0.070	0.085
NH ₃ CrackT, °C	469	449	–	–
AOG recirculation fraction, –	0.830	0.830	0.880	0.880
RFR, mol/s	0.232	0.408	0.069	0.226
AOG CondT, °C	44	59	37	72
ΔT, °C	100	100	100	100
Anode ΔP, mbar	40	68	9	33
Cathode ΔP, mbar	28	22	35	30
K _n , –	0.107	0.073	–	–
K _{n,crt} , –	0.131	0.131	–	–
NH ₃ cracking fraction, –	0.928	0.883	–	–
Single pass fuel utilization, –	0.621	0.300	0.891	0.347
Global fuel utilization, –	0.908	0.720	0.986	0.817
Air flow to stack, mol/s	1.510	1.175	1.844	1.594
Air flow to burner, mol/s	0.054	0.226	0.007	0.134
Flow to burner, mol/s	0.046	0.082	0.009	0.031
Air blower power, kW	0.32	0.25	0.39	0.34
AOG blower power, kW	0.25	0.55	0.01	0.27
Net power production, kW	10.49	10.46	10.50	10.51
Total energy input, kW	16.23	20.49	16.93	20.46
Electrical efficiency, %	64.65	51.05	61.99	51.37
Heat exergy, kW	1.70	2.78	3.03	4.03
Overall exergy efficiency, %	75.12	64.61	79.89	71.06
Electricity from RC, kW	3.13	4.62	3.88	5.00
Electrical efficiency with RC, %	83.91	73.58	84.91	75.80

space. This analysis identifies which decision variables strongly influence the objective functions, whether through complementary or opposing effects. It also guides the refinement of strategies for adjusting these variables to better meet system performance goals, offering a clearer understanding of the system's operational limitations.

4.2. Impact of decision variables on the NH₃-fueled SOFC system performance

For the obtained Pareto front, it is observed that certain decision variables demonstrate constrained variability, as presented in Table 4 (Pareto solutions). For example, the condensation temperature for AOG recirculation ranges from 43 to 60 °C. The AOG recirculation fraction remains fairly stable between 0.72 and 0.89, and the temperature difference across the stack consistently hovers around 100 °C. The ammonia cracker temperature fluctuates between 449 and 479 °C. A lower cracker temperature does not automatically lead to nitriding, potentially due to the high hydrogen content resulting from AOG recirculation. Lastly, the fuel input shows some variation, ranging from 0.051 to 0.067 mol/s. Table 4 also presents results from running the SOFC model (i.e., Monte Carlo solutions) without targeting objective functions by using the lower and upper limits for decision variables from Table 2. As expected, the Pareto solutions have narrower ranges, a direct consequence of the optimization process steering search towards specific directions.

In the context of studying correlations between decision variables and objective functions, examining the complete feasible domain provides a comprehensive understanding of the system behaviour. Therefore, this section constructs correlations using feasible solutions from Monte Carlo simulations rather than focusing solely on optimal solutions identified by the system optimization. Further, to ensure equitable comparisons among the decision variables, their values have been normalized. It is also important to note that as the AOG recirculation fraction increases, the recirculation flow rate (RFR) also increases non-linearly. As the AOG recirculation fraction is challenging to measure directly, therefore, in

Table 4Ranges of Pareto front and Monte Carlo solutions for NH₃-fueled SOFC system.

	Pareto front solutions	Monte Carlo solutions
NH ₃ cracker temperature, °C	449–479	417–500
NH ₃ input, mol/s	0.051–0.067	0.051–0.067
AOG recirculation fraction, –	0.72–0.89	0.28–0.90
AOG recirculation condensation temperature, °C	43.1–60.3	35–280
Temperature difference across stack, °C	99.2–100	30.8–100
NH ₃ external cracking fraction, –	0.88–0.94	0.74–0.94
AOG recirculation flow rate (RFR), m ³ /s	0.019–0.045	0.0042–0.051
Electrical efficiency, %	48.3–65.0	40.5–64.7
Global fuel utilization, –	0.69–0.90	0.68–0.90
Heat exergy, kW	1.70–3.00	0.63–3.00

* It has been computed using AOG recirculation fraction.

subsequent analyses, the RFR is primarily used to assess the system performance.

Fig. 4 illustrates the correlations between five independent decision variables and three performance criteria. An analysis of electrical efficiency, highlighted in pale blue, reveals that an increase in certain variables negatively influences electrical efficiency. These include AOG RFR, AOG recirculation condensation temperature (CondT), NH₃ fuel input (FI) and NH₃ cracker temperature (CrackT).

Analyzing these relationships reveals that lower RFR reduces AOG blower power consumption, thereby enhancing system efficiency. Similarly, the low value of CondT allows the cooler to condense more water, reducing the flow that must pass through the AOG blower and subsequently lowering the power consumption. Moreover, a reduction in fuel input correlates with increased electrical efficiency, directly reflecting a decrease in chemical energy input. Additionally, a lower value of CrackT results in a reduced ammonia conversion rate, allowing more ammonia to undergo internal cracking within the stack. Since this reaction is endothermic, it offsets some of the heat released by the exothermic electro-

Fig. 4. Correlations between decision variables and objective functions for the NH_3 -fueled SOFC system.

Table 5

NH_3 -fueled SOFC system: coefficients (with 95% confidence intervals) of linear correlations between decision variables and objective functions.

Decision Variables	Coefficients (C_i)		
	Electrical efficiency, %	Heat exergy, kW	Global fuel utilisation, –
Intercept (C_0)	108.57 ± 3.29	-2.86 ± 0.97	1.55 ± 0.01
RFR, m^3/s	-144.28 ± 9.50	3.93 ± 1.38	–
CondT, $^\circ\text{C}$	-0.030 ± 0.001	-0.0021 ± 0.0002	$-9.24\text{E-}6$
FI, mol/s	-683.14 ± 20.16	72.82 ± 2.92	$\pm 3.70\text{E-}6$
ΔT , $^\circ\text{C}$	0.046 ± 0.005	0.0137 ± 0.0007	12.87 ± 0.06
CrackT, $^\circ\text{C}$	-0.032 ± 0.006	-0.0018 ± 0.0009	–
Fitting performance, R^2	0.883	0.773	0.994

chemical reactions, thereby reducing the need for cathode airflow and decreasing the power consumption by the air blower, ultimately enhancing the electrical efficiency. Conversely, a higher temperature difference across the stack (ΔT) tends to increase electrical efficiency, as a greater ΔT decreases the necessary air flow rate.

For GFU, the fuel input emerges as the predominant variable (Fig. 4, columns highlighted in black); a lower fuel input corresponds to a higher GFU. Reduced fuel input implies that the stack receives precisely the correct quantity of fuel to produce electricity according to its designed capacity, thereby pushing the system towards a high single-pass fuel utilization as most of the fuel is converted into electricity. Consequently, minimal residual fuel at the downstream of the stack leads to a high GFU. Interestingly, a lower AOG recirculation condensation temperature increases GFU, though its impact is minor compared to that of the fuel input to the stack. The relation of GFU to other variables seems to have no statistical significance.

Finally, impacts on the heat exergy are highlighted in dark green (Fig. 4). An increase in the fuel input positively impacts the heat exergy, which aligns with the expectation. Given that the stack area is fixed, when fuel input increases while electricity production remains nearly constant, more fuel is channelled to the burner for complete combustion at around $900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This mechanism effectively enhances the heat distribution across different temperature levels, thus elevating the overall heat exergy of the system. Similarly, an increase in the AOG RFR positively impacts heat exergy. This effect arises because the recirculated flow must be cooled to a specified temperature to condense a designated amount of water. As a large RFR is involved in this cooling process, a larger quantity of heat is released across various temperature levels, thereby increasing the system's heat potential. This principle also applies to the AOG

CondT, where lower temperatures positively influence the exergy by modifying the thermal profile of the system. Moreover, a higher ΔT positively influences heat exergy, whereas an increased CrackT tends to reduce heat exergy. Thus, analyzing the available heat at different temperature levels could enhance understanding of the complexities associated with heat exergy, as it directly relates to its calculation. This deeper insight could reveal more about the dynamics of thermal energy management within the system.

To simplify the process for industrial professionals and laboratory researchers seeking key performance indicators such as electrical efficiency, global fuel utilization and heat exergy, Table 5 presents the linear coefficients for the decision variables in their actual units without normalization. This allows for the straightforward incorporation of measured data into the specified mathematical equations, simplifying the estimation of key indicators. It also predicts substantial gains/losses in performance indicators with respect to changes in the decision variables. Finally, 95% confidence intervals and the R^2 parameter are displayed to quantify the robustness of the estimated coefficients and the fitting performance of the linear regression. Interestingly, this approach yields promising mathematical correlations/surrogate models for electrical efficiency and global fuel utilization. Conversely, the use of the surrogate model for heat exergy should be considered carefully due to the higher uncertainty.

4.2.1. Heat analysis with temperature levels

Fig. 5 presents the impact of decision variables on the heat exergy available from the SOFC system, which is computed using the heat available from the system at different temperature levels. Thus, understanding the impact of decision variables on the heat available at different temperature levels is crucial. This study divides the heat from the SOFC system into three categories:

Fig. 5. Impact of decision variables on different temperature heat levels.

high-temperature heat (above 600 °C), medium-temperature heat (between 400 and 600 °C), and low-temperature heat (below 400 °C). This categorization enhances our understanding of heat distribution within the system. Fig. 5 visualizes correlations between decision variables and available heat at three different temperature levels.

AOG RFR positively impacts the availability of low-temperature heat. For larger RFR, the water condensation at low temperatures releases a large quantity of heat. The medium- and high-temperature heat from the cooling of RFR is reused for heating of RFR after the AOG blower. With an increase in RFR, the ammonia input to the external cracker also increases, which requires additional medium/high-temperature heat for the ammonia cracking. AOG CondT has a negative impact on total heat availability from the system. No water is condensed near the upper limit (280 °C) of CondT. In that case, the heat released by the cooling before the AOG blower is reused in the heating after the AOG blower. When the CondT is near the lower limit, the maximum amount of the water is condensed, and the maximum amount of heat is released by cooling and condensation of water molecules. As CondT increases from the lower limit to the upper limit, it has a negative impact on the availability of heat, which is more prominent in low-temperature heat.

FI has a positive impact on the availability of total heat from the system. As explained in the previous section, an increase in the FI does not significantly improve the electricity output due to the fixed area of the stack. Hence, the extra fuel is not utilized inside the stack and is subsequently combusted in the burner, resulting in more available heat in the flue gases at different temperature levels. FI has the most dominant impact on the low-temperature heat, which has the largest temperature range and includes water condensation. ΔT has a positive impact on the high-temperature heat from the system. A high-temperature difference corresponds to a lower temperature at the inlet of the stack. It indicates a substantial heating of low-temperature flow at the stack inlet to high-temperature (up to 750 °C) at the stack outlet. This suggests that heat is being effectively upgraded within the system.

Finally, CrackT has a mixed impact on available heat at different temperature levels. A high value of CrackT leads to reduced availability of high-temperature heat. This reduction is mainly because higher CrackT enhances ammonia cracking, which in turn requires more high-temperature heat within the ammonia cracker, subsequently decreasing its availability. The use of high-temperature heat increases the availability of medium-temperature heat from the system. Conversely, a low value of CrackT will utilize medium-temperature heat, and more high-temperature heat will be available from the system.

Fig. 6. Evaluation of pressure drops for both anode and cathode sides and nitriding impact for NH_3 -fueled SOFC systems under various AOG RFR (recirculation flow rate) and CrackT (cracker temperature).

Overall, this section provides detailed insights into the system's thermal dynamics, highlighting how decision variables affect the quality of available heat. The findings reveal the delicate balance needed to manage heat exergy effectively. These insights are essential for informing future system designs and guiding research efforts to enhance system performance and heat integration.

4.2.2. NH_3 -SOFC system design considerations

Two critical constraints have been integrated into the SOFC system model: the pressure drop across the stack and the potential for stack nitriding to enhance the realism of model outcomes and offer practical guidelines. After analyzing all solutions, they can be categorized into three groups: those meeting the pressure drop constraint (ΔP), those meeting the nitriding constraint, and those satisfying both. As shown in Fig. 6, points highlighted in grey colour, representing compliance with the pressure drop constraint, illustrate that this criterion is usually independent of the CrackT but significantly constrained by the AOG RFR. This is logical as higher RFRs have higher velocity through the stack, thus increasing the pressure drops. These considerations constrain the RFR between 0 and 0.05 m^3/s .

Points in green colour denote solutions that meet the nitriding constraint. These points are generally independent of the AOG RFR, as the ammonia cracker can effectively crack most of the ammonia. However, compliance with this constraint depends on the CrackT, requiring it to be above 400 °C to ensure that more than 65% of

NH₃ is cracked. Finally, the points highlighted in purple colour represent solutions that satisfy both constraints. These results indicate that lower CrackT can still prevent nitriding impact, provided there is a high AOG RFR. However, this high flow rate may lead to excessive pressure drop. The pressure drop is associated with design and manufacturing, and variations in nitriding potential can occur. Despite these uncertainties, the findings offer valuable insights into the interactions between CrackT, AOG RFR, and operational constraints. These insights are useful for optimizing the design and operation of the SOFC system.

4.3. Impact of decision variables on the H₂-fueled SOFC system performance

As presented in Table 6, the Monte Carlo simulations have explored a broader decision variable space. This exploration is utilized to develop comprehensive mathematical correlations. These feasible solutions may not achieve the maximum values of various objective functions, as reaching the optimum is not the primary goal of employing the Monte Carlo method. Instead, the focus is on capturing a wide array of possible outcomes to understand the underlying relationships and impacts thoroughly.

Fig. 7 presents correlations between four decision variables and three objective functions. A higher AOG RFR is observed to negatively impact electrical efficiency, primarily due to increased AOG blower power consumption. This finding seems counter-intuitive as AOG recirculation is thought to enhance electrical efficiency. However, this improvement occurs under specific conditions that will be discussed later in the analysis. Additionally, a higher CondT reduces electrical efficiency because it increases the steam content in the AOG recirculation, which not only raises AOG blower power consumption but also reduces stack output power due to the dilution from steam. Conversely, reducing FI leads to an increase in electrical efficiency. Lastly, a greater ΔT reduces the need for airflow on the cathode side, lowering air blower power consumption and enhancing system electrical efficiency. For GFU, FI is identified as the dominant factor with a substantial negative impact, while AOG RFR and CondT exhibit slight positive effects on GFU, with the underlying reasons detailed previously for the NH₃-fueled system. Moving to the analysis of heat exergy, the conclusions align with those for NH₃-fueled system: AOG RFR, FI and ΔT positively influence heat exergy. In contrast, AOG recirculation CondT has a negative impact.

The primary distinction between NH₃- and H₂-fueled systems lies in the relative impact of the decision variables on the heat exergy. In the NH₃-fueled system, FI has the most significant impact; however, in the H₂-fueled system, ΔT exerts the strongest positive influence on heat exergy. This difference is primarily because the electrochemical reactions in the H₂-fueled system are exothermic, lacking the endothermic (internal) ammonia cracking reaction that balances heat in the NH₃-fueled system. Consequently, the H₂-fueled system requires a much larger cathode airflow compared to the NH₃-fueled system, significantly outweighing other system flows, such as FI, which leads to a more pronounced impact on the heat exergy for the NH₃-fueled system.

Table 7 displays the coefficients of linear correlations between objective functions and decision variables to simplify the presentation for industrial practitioners and academic researchers. The table also includes data on the fitting performance of the linear models. By employing these linear correlations, it is possible to predict the system's performance in advance. This predictive capability can save time during the system design phase and assist in refining the system's architecture, ultimately facilitating more efficient and effective system design. These surrogate models are highly reliable, with a maximum of 10% deviation for the heat exergy.

Table 6
Ranges of Pareto front and Monte Carlo solutions for H₂-fueled SOFC system.

	Pareto front solutions	Monte Carlo solutions
H ₂ input, mol/s	0.070–0.080	0.070–0.085
AOG recirculation fraction, –	0.84–0.88	0–0.9
AOG recirculation condensation temperature, °C	36.4–88.0	35–280
Temperature difference across stack, °C	97.9–98.7	30–100
AOG recirculation flow rate ^a , m ³ /s	0.006–0.019	0–0.057
Electrical efficiency, %	51.4–61.9	38.8–61.9
Global fuel utilization, –	0.82–0.98	0.81–0.98
Heat exergy, kW	3.03–4.03	0.16–3.67

^aIt has been computed using AOG recirculation fraction.

4.3.1. H₂-SOFC system design considerations

The previous findings indicate that a higher AOG RFR negatively impacts electrical efficiency while only slightly enhancing GFU. It is essential to analyze the combined impact of single-pass fuel utilization (SFU) and AOG recirculation on the stack's performance to gain a deeper understanding of these effects. The results of MOO are used as the dataset for this exploration, which allows for a concentrated examination of how these two factors interact and influence electrical efficiency. As previously discussed, the AOG RFR shows a more substantial impact than the AOG recirculation fraction due to their strong non-linear relationship. Consequently, in this section, the AOG recirculation fraction/ratio is utilized as the decision variable, which allows for a more precise analysis of recirculation's influence on the system performance. This analysis aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the balance between AOG recirculation and SFU for optimizing the system's electrical efficiency.

Fig. 8(a–c) illustrate the directional impact of SFU on the electrical efficiency of the system, dividing the analysis into three distinct regimes based on SFU values. As shown in Fig. 8(a), when the stack operates inefficiently ($0.3 < \text{SFU} < 0.6$), the majority of high SFU points stay in the positive impact region, demonstrating that an increase in SFU from 0.3 to 0.6 brings a positive impact on the electrical efficiency. Conversely, as illustrated in Fig. 8(b), when the stack operates within a moderate range ($0.6 < \text{SFU} < 0.8$), the expected trend from the inefficient stack operation is no longer observed. In this SFU range, even at lower SFU values (around 0.6), electrical efficiency can have a significant positive impact. It is also interesting to note that when SFU is high (near 0.8), it can adversely affect electrical efficiency. Finally, when the stack operation is outstanding ($0.8 < \text{SFU} < 0.9$), as presented in Fig. 8(c), SFU brings a positive impact on electrical efficiency.

Fig. 8(d) explores the correlation among AOG recirculation fraction/ratio, SFU and electrical efficiency, shedding light on why moderate SFU levels can positively impact efficiency. When SFU is below 0.6, increasing the AOG recirculation fraction indeed improves efficiency, though it is not able to reach the optimum efficiency. In such cases, the most effective strategy tends to be enhancing the stack's operational efficiency itself. However, when the stack operates moderately well, such that SFU is greater than 0.6 but not exceeding 0.8, then the result shows that high electrical efficiency can be achieved for SFU near the lower bound, thanks to a high AOG recirculation fraction. This suggests that AOG recirculation significantly boosts efficiency when the stack operates sub-optimally but within a reasonable performance range. Conversely, when SFU exceeds 0.8, indicating highly efficient stack operation, the high AOG recirculation fraction begins to deteriorate efficiency. When stack efficiently converts most of the chemical energy into electricity, additional AOG recirculation does not yield sufficient benefits to offset the energy consumed by the AOG blower.

Fig. 7. Correlations between decision variables and objective functions for the H₂-fueled SOFC system.

Table 7

H₂-fueled SOFC system: coefficients (with 95% confidence intervals) of linear correlations between decision variables and objective functions.

Decision Variables	Coefficients (C _i)		
	Electrical efficiency, %	Heat exergy, kW	Global fuel utilisation, –
Intercept (C ₀)	116.88 ± 1.16	–1.98 ± 0.29	1.780 ± 0.004
RFR, m ³ /s	–19.41 ± 0.85	1.11 ± 0.14	0.0026 ± 0.0014
CondT, °C	–0.024 ± 0.001	–0.0030 ± 0.0002	–8.63E-6 ± 1.87E-6
FI, mol/s	–824.06 ± 18.23	21.84 ± 3.08	–11.43 ± 0.03
ΔT, °C	0.056 ± 0.004	0.0374 ± 0.0006	–
Fitting performance, R ²	0.933	0.894	0.998

Operating a stack with a very high SFU involves precise tuning of FI to match the electricity production specified by the stack manufacturer. While it can enhance electrical efficiency, it may also reduce the stack lifetime due to the deficient concentration of unconverted fuel at the stack outlet. The low cell voltage is then very sensitive to small variations, which must be avoided in industrial settings. Introducing additional fuel beyond the optimal value into the stack is common. This precaution prevents leakage and reduces the potential degradation, thereby safeguarding the lifetime of the system. The findings from this study suggest a more balanced approach: operating the stack at moderate SFU levels

can yield promising system performance while minimizing the risk of damaging the stack. This strategy allows for a safer and potentially more sustainable operation, aligning operational practices with longevity and efficiency goals.

4.4. Development of soft sensors for the safe operation of the system

The pressure drop is implemented as a constraint for both SOFC systems, which depends on stack manufacturing requirements. Thus, the maximum pressure drop value is not the primary concern; understanding its correlation with key operational param-

Fig. 8. (a–c) Directional impact of SFU on electrical efficiency, and (d) correlation among AOG recirculation fraction/ratio, SFU and electrical efficiency.

Fig. 9. Correlations between decision variables and pressure drop for (a) NH_3 - and (b) H_2 -fueled systems.

ters is crucial for maintaining stack in safe operational zones. Fig. 9 illustrates pressure drops on the cathode and anode sides of the systems.

The AOG RFR has the maximum positive impact on the anode side pressure drop in both cases. This is logical, as the RFR is mixed with the FI and then injected into the anode side of the stack, changing the pressure drop. In the NH_3 -fueled system, higher AOG recirculation means more ammonia is returned back to the stack, facilitating additional internal ammonia cracking, balancing the heat from the electrochemical reactions and thus reducing the cathode air flow rate. This principle also applies to the AOG recirculation CondT. For FI in both cases, an increase in flow rate positively affects the pressure drop on the anode side NH_3 FI negatively impacts the cathode side pressure drop because it reduces the air flow rate. ΔT has a negative impact on the pressure drop, while CrackT has a positive impact. The rationale behind these impacts was thoroughly detailed in the previous sections, which outlined how these factors influence the operational safe zones of the system. This explanation contextualizes the impacts of decision variables in maintaining operational stability and safety.

However, measuring the pressure drop across the stack in real-world conditions can be challenging and costly since sensors may degrade in high-temperature environments. Some designs thus install pressure sensors in contact with the cold side. Nevertheless, having too many physical sensors not only increases initial installation costs but also increases ongoing maintenance expenses. In light of these challenges, exploring alternative methods, such as soft sensors, presents significant advantages to the SOFC systems. Soft sensors utilize mathematical models and system inputs to estimate conditions, offering a cost-effective alternative to tradi-

tional sensors. They also provide real-time monitoring and predictive control capabilities, which are essential for managing the dynamics of the system. Soft sensors can act as an early warning system by predicting critical conditions that could lead to system failures, such as excessive pressure drops. This enhances the safety protocols of the system operation, ensuring better operational management and system safety without the need for extensive physical sensing infrastructure.

As detailed in Table 8, the mathematical models for estimating the pressure drops in both systems have been presented, utilizing only the easy-to-monitor variables. The high R^2 values affirm robust fitting performance of models, instilling confidence in their predictive accuracy. Implementing these soft sensors eliminates dependency on specific pressure values determined by the stack manufacturer, thus broadening their applicability. This approach can significantly ease the burden of plant engineers involved in the monitoring of plant operations and prevent delays in delivering crucial sensor information to the control system, enhancing operational responsiveness and safety.

Another soft sensor that could be integrated into the NH_3 -fueled SOFC systems is the nitriding alarm. In real-world applications, the safe operation of this system is ensured when nitriding potential (K_n) is kept below a critical threshold ($K_{n,crt}$). While the former depends on the molar composition at the anode inlet, the latter is a complex function of the stack operating temperature. Simple linear regression is inadequate for making good predictions. Therefore, this analysis aims to find a balanced mathematical representation of nitriding impact using polynomials up to the 3rd degree. This expression should provide a reasonable and reliable prediction of the nitriding impact with the fewest possible terms.

Table 8
Coefficients (with 95% confidence intervals) of linear correlations between decision variables and pressure drops for two systems.

Decision Variables	Coefficients (C_i)			
	NH ₃ -fueled SOFC system		H ₂ -fueled SOFC system	
	Anode ΔP , mbar	Cathode ΔP , mbar	Anode ΔP , mbar	Cathode ΔP , mbar
Intercept (C_0)	-17.49 ± 2.29	91.01 ± 3.05	33.62 ± 23.19	58.60 ± 1.07
RFR, m ³ /s	1794.69 ± 13.08	-176.81 ± 30.71	133.35 ± 1.81	-24.23 ± 2.83
CondT, °C	0.0360 ± 0.002	0.0181 ± 0.004	0.049 ± 0.002	–
FI, mol/s	219.97 ± 27.76	-246.57 ± 65.20	-379.62 ± 44.66	839.25 ± 77.91
ΔT , °C	-0.048 ± 0.007	-0.901 ± 0.016	-0.025 ± 0.010	-0.852 ± 0.017
CrackT, °C	0.036 ± 0.009	0.077 ± 0.021		
Fitting performance, R^2	0.988	0.905	0.948	0.864

Fig. 10. (a) Different trials (1 million runs) and best-fitted solutions for a different number of terms, and (b) Parity plot for $K_{n,diff}$ using mathematical representation with ten terms.

Fig. 10(a) shows the fitting performance (R^2 -score) for one million random combinations of the decision variables (d_i) to predict $K_{n,diff}$. Obviously, for safe operation, the parameter $K_{n,diff}$ should be greater than 0. The maximum allowed complexity of the mathematical representation is illustrated in Eq. (5).

In Fig. 10(a), a prediction error of about 10% can be achieved with ten terms. More complex equations generally result in better fits, but a trade-off solution with ten terms is chosen since doubling the number of terms increases precision only by 4%. Eq. (6) provides the mathematical formula for $K_{n,diff}$ with ten terms, and Fig. 10(b) shows the parity plot between the actual values and model predictions. Several second-degree and mixed terms are present in the mathematical formula, which captures the non-linear phenomenon accurately. The decision variables include AOG CondT (in °C), AOG RFR (in m³/s), NH₃ FI (in mol/s), ΔT (in °C), and CrackT (in °C). This equation provides a robust representation of the nitriding impact as a function of easily monitored variables.

Contrarily to linear regression models in previous sections, it is difficult to deduce which are the most impacting variables here, as only real coefficients are provided. However, some interesting conclusions can be drawn. Firstly, a larger ΔT , resulting in a lower stack inlet temperature, definitely has a positive effect on nitriding. Also, given the range of the AOG RFR ($RFR_{max} \ll 1$), this variable also appears to favour the safe operation as it dilutes the NH₃ concentration in the anode inlet flow rate, resulting in lower nitriding potential.

$$K_{n,crit} - K_n = K_{n,diff} \propto f(d_1, d_2, d_3, d_4, d_5)^3 \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_{n,crit} = & -5.13 + 3.34 \cdot RFR + 2.12 \cdot FI + 0.02 \cdot CrackT \\
 & - 5.09 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot CondT - 28.07 \cdot RFR^2 - 2.04 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot CrackT^2 \\
 & + 2.57 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot \Delta T^2 + 1.40 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot CondT^2 \\
 & + 6.49 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot (CrackT \cdot \Delta T)
 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

4.5. General discussions

4.5.1. Soft sensors robustness

The robustness and generalizability of the mathematical correlations or soft sensors are supported by the extensive range of decision variables considered and the statistical significance of the linear regression. For instance, the AOG recirculation fraction spans from 0 to 0.9, accommodating configurations from no AOG recirculation to nearly complete recirculation. The AOG condensation temperature range from 35 to 280 °C, indicating possible cold or warm recirculation, with hot recirculation excluded due to cost and efficiency considerations. Furthermore, only the stack outlet temperature is fixed, allowing the system to determine the necessary airflow to balance heat within the stack and respect maximum temperature difference across the stack. Additionally, similar findings emerge in the analysis of soft sensors for pressure drops across the stack. While the R^2 for the cathode pressure drop is 0.9 and for the anode, it is around 0.99, system analysis indicates that the anode pressure drop is typically higher than that at the cathode (Table 2).

However, the applicability of these models may be limited by specific components, such as the ammonia cracker, which is highly dependent on the catalyst used. Nevertheless, correlations suggest that ammonia cracking has minimal impact on efficiency and fuel utilization, primarily affecting heat management. Furthermore, while this study assumes that the stack operates at full load, exploring part-load operation could expand the operational boundaries. Previous studies indicate that stack efficiency may increase under part-load conditions, suggesting that the results presented here could be viewed as conservative estimates. Consequently, incorporating part-load operation into future research could yield intriguing insights and potentially enhance our understanding of system performance across different operational states.

Overall, the soft sensors developed in this study can serve as preliminary performance estimation tools for both industrial engi-

neers and academic researchers, allowing them to gauge performance prior to implementing costly actions.

4.5.2. Industrial applications

This study employs a 10 kW system as an example, recognizing that while most outcomes can linearly be scaled up, this raises several pertinent questions about the practical implementation of optimal solutions and their scalability. Importantly, it should be noted that maintaining continuous operation at maximum efficiency points in industrial settings is challenging. However, the soft sensors developed in this study can interface with the real-time optimization setups to predict operational adjustments.

Furthermore, if a customer prioritizes system efficiency, the results indicate that cold AOG recirculation significantly enhances it. Accordingly, the pipeline size for AOG recirculation could be standardized to manage this flow rate effectively. For a large size system, centralizing all cold AOG recirculation-related balance-of-plant components could reduce costs. Typically, conventional AOG blowers designed for large flow rates are more economical, similar to burner systems. Moreover, centralizing the burner system allows for the collection and utilization of heat in a standard-size Rankine cycle.

The centralization versus decentralization of SOFC systems emerges as a compelling topic for further in-depth research, considering economic, sustainability, and energy indicators, though it extends beyond the scope of this study. This future work could inform the strategic deployment of SOFC technologies in various applications.

5. Conclusions

This study conducts a detailed analysis of ammonia and hydrogen as fuels for SOFC systems, revealing nuanced performance differences. The ammonia-fueled system achieves a maximum efficiency of about 65%, slightly surpassing the efficiency (62%) reached by the hydrogen-fueled system. This enhanced efficiency with ammonia can be attributed to its endothermic internal cracking reaction but also its higher number of electrons involved in the electrochemical reaction. Conversely, the hydrogen-fueled system demonstrates superior global fuel utilization compared to the ammonia-fueled system. This difference is mainly due to nitriding risks for ammonia, which necessitate maintaining a certain proportion of unconverted fuel downstream of the stack.

The analysis also delves into the thermal analysis of both systems. It reveals that the hydrogen-fueled system exhibits a higher heat exergy of 3.88 kW, in contrast to 1.7 kW for the ammonia-fueled system, demonstrating a greater availability of usable heat. Both systems can function as co-generation units, serving not only as efficient electricity generators but also as heat suppliers across various temperature levels, akin to boilers. The optimal utilization of this heat remains a challenge. One promising strategy involves the integration of a Rankine cycle (RC) to convert waste heat into additional electricity. Without the application of RC, the NH₃-fueled system can achieve an overall heat exergy efficiency of 75%, and electrical efficiency can reach 84% after implementing the waste heat valorization technique or RC. Meanwhile, the H₂-fueled system can attain an overall heat exergy efficiency of 80%, and, after integration with an RC, it can reach an 85% electrical efficiency.

The study also analyzed the impact of decision variables on the system performance for both NH₃- and H₂-fueled SOFC systems by applying Monte Carlo simulations. In the NH₃-fueled system, AOG recirculation flow rate and condensation temperature, fuel input and cracker temperature negatively impact the electrical efficiency. Conversely, the temperature difference across the stack exerts a positive influence on the electrical efficiency. Regarding heat exergy, AOG recirculation flow rate, fuel input and stack temperature

difference positively affect heat exergy, while AOG recirculation condensation temperature and cracker temperature have detrimental effects. Similar trends are observed for H₂-fueled systems, underscoring the consistent impacts of these variables across different fuel types. The study further dissects heat exergy by splitting it into three temperature levels to comprehensively understand the impact of each decision variable across temperature levels.

One of the novelties of this study is the incorporation of real-world industrial constraints, specifically pressure drops and nitriding potential, into the system model. Such integration ensures that the findings are not only theoretically sound but also practically viable, offering actionable insights for safe and efficient operation. For the NH₃-fueled system, the anode side pressure drop is primarily influenced by the AOG recirculation flow rate and shows little dependence on the cracker temperature. In contrast, adherence to the nitriding constraint depends on maintaining the cracker temperature above 400 °C to ensure sufficient ammonia cracking, with minimal reliance on flow rate variations. These constraints narrow the feasible solution space for the system. For the H₂-fueled system, the analysis delves into the combined impact of SFU and AOG recirculation on the system performance. It underscores the importance of balancing these factors to optimize electrical efficiency and highlights the substantial, though not dominant, impact of AOG recirculation on electrical efficiency. The findings suggest that SFU within a range of 0.6 to 0.8 not only achieves good performance but also potentially extends the lifetime of the stack.

Finally, to facilitate the practical applications based on this study, various mathematical correlations have been developed for key performance indicators. These mathematical formulas utilize easily measurable variables, making it straightforward for engineers and researchers to apply the findings effectively. Further research is warranted in the field of SOFC systems, particularly regarding nitriding effects, where experimental data remains limited. More extensive testing could provide additional validation of the models. Additionally, the impact of pressure drop constraint is closely tied to the stack manufacturing design. While the optimal solutions identified here may vary under different constraints, this does not detract from the validity of the trends and correlations observed in the current analysis.

In summary, this comprehensive study not only advances our understanding of SOFC system performance using ammonia and hydrogen as fuels but also integrates critical operational constraints to enhance practical applications. The comparative performance analysis, alongside thermal analysis and decision variable impacts, provides a robust framework for future research and development in SOFC technology. By addressing both theoretical and practical aspects, the study lays a foundation for optimizing SOFC systems to meet diverse energy needs efficiently and safely, ultimately contributing to a more sustainable and energy-efficient world.

Future research could focus on dynamic optimization of the stack, environmental impact analysis of different fuels used in SOFC systems, and cost analysis employing a modularity approach. These research studies have great potential to enhance the industrial applicability of SOFC technology, addressing both performance and sustainability aspects.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Xinyi Wei: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Arthur Waeber:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Shivom Sharma:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology. **Ligang Wang:** Supervision, Validation. **Stefan Diethelm:** Validation, Supervision. **François Maréchal:** Supervision, Resources. **Jan Van herle:** Supervision, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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